

Efficiency of Android Malware detection using Machine Learning Algorithms: Random Forest, K-NN and Decision Tree

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Abstract— Because of its widespread use, the Android has become a major target for security concerns. Malware-infected apps are flooding third-party app markets. It is unquestionably vital to have a reliable method of detecting malware and so controlling its growth. Researchers are currently investigating machine learning approaches for detecting malware using static and/or dynamic information derived from an Android application package file. In this study, we compare three classifiers for identifying malicious and benign android applications using static features: Decision Tree, K-Nearest Neighbor, and Random Forest. Among the three Random Forest proved to be the most accurate.

Keywords— *malware, malicious, Machine Learning, Android Malware*

I. INTRODUCTION

Smartphones have become an inextricable element of our daily lives in the modern world. In 2022, there were more than 6.64 billion smartphone users throughout the world. With a worldwide market share of 71 percent, Android OS is the most popular mobile operating system. People from all walks of life now have access to inexpensive and simple-to-use smartphones thanks to the open source operating system. However, because of its widespread use, Android has become a favourite target for hackers looking to exploit security flaws and get access to sensitive data According to a McAfee report, over 35 million Android malicious applications were discovered in 2019. Existing signature-based technologies are having a hard time detecting new malware variants. Researchers are experimenting with machine learning methods as a solution. although the various table text styles are provided.

In this research, we compare three machine learning classifiers for identifying android malware using static features: Decision Tree, K-Nearest Neighbor, and Random Forest. Two datasets were gathered from the public domain, developed using Drebin and Malgenome, two of the most well-known Android malware repositories. The data was pre-processed before being combined.

The Random Forest was perhaps the most accurate of the three algorithms, with an accuracy score of 0.963 compared to 0.961 for both KNN and Decision Tree, as well as an F1-score of 0.947, Precision of 0.964, and recall of 0.931.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

ZHUO MA, HAORAN GE, YANG LIU, MENG ZHAO, and JIANFENG MA [1], in their paper A Combination Method for Android Malware Detection Based on Control Flow Graphs and Machine Learning Algorithms, present methods to detect Android malwares using three types of system API data sets: API usage data, API frequency data sets, and API sequence data sets. Each model's performance is measured using standard classification metrics including Precision, Recall, and F-score, and the performance is evaluated.

Diyana Tehraniy Dehkordy and Abbas Rasoolzadegan[2], in their work A new machine learning-based technique for android malware detection on an unbalanced dataset, employ a method to identify malware and categorise apps. To extract characteristics from apps, static analysis was used. Because the number of retrieved characteristics was so enormous, preprocessing was used to rank them and delete the ones that were unsuccessful. According to the findings, the highest frequency of characteristics should not be employed to build a malware detection model. As a result, feature preprocessing is required to increase the malware detection process' accuracy.

Hyoil Han, SeungJin Lim, Kyoungwon Suh, Seonghyun Park, Seong-je Cho, and Minkyu Park [3], in their study Enhanced Android Malware Detection: An SVM-based Machine Learning Approach, focused on the static analysis of Android apps' API calls. They used Support Vector Machines (SVM) to test 58,602 applications and 133,227 features were taken for detecting malwares in apps, and the results were reasonable when compared with existing techniques.

Mohsen Kakavand, Mohammad Dabbagh, and Ali Dehghantanha [4], in their paper Application of Machine Learning Algorithms for Android Malware Detection, used keywords as the main malware detection features with the aim of evaluating, perhaps looking for keywords in both the permissions sought in an app's manifest file and the system call logs may yield better results than looking at specific features. To classify Android applications into benign or malicious, they used and compared two ML techniques named SVM and KNN.

Omar N. Elayan and Ahmad M. Mustafa [5], in their study Android Malware Detection Using Deep Learning, proposed a novel model for detecting malware in Android OS. A comparison of classic machine learning techniques and deep learning approaches is presented in order to pick the most effective method that detects Android malware with the best possible outcomes. The suggested classifiers were trained on a dataset derived from the CICAndMal2017 dataset, which was assessed using a static analysis of genuine and realistic malware and benign Android app samples. The research included both permissions and API requests, as utilising both shown that it was worthwhile to place a greater emphasis on identifying Android malware models.

III. MOTIVATION

As the cost of these devices has reduced and the capability and services provided have improved, the use of mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets has grown significantly in recent years. Because of its accessibility and open availability, the Android OS is now becoming not just a crucial stakeholder in the mobile device business, but also an appealing target for hackers. Because of the risk of data theft that mobile phone users confront, malware detection on Android devices is now a more serious issue in cyber security. Traditional solutions, such as signature-based procedures, are insufficient to protect users against new varieties of Android malware's rising complexity and quick behaviour changes. As a result, a lot of work has been done recently to define and generalise the dangerous behaviour patterns of mobile applications for malware detection using machine learning models and algorithms.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The obtained datasets were initially pre-processed and merged. After that, we divided it into test and training sets. The train set was subjected to feature selection, and machine learning models were trained on it. After that, each classifier's hyperparameters were tweaked using the train set and stratified 10-fold cross validation. Finally, the test set is utilised to evaluate the classification models using the hyperparameter value that was supplied. In addition to accuracy, assessment metrics such as precision, recall, and f1-score were used to address the dataset's class imbalance problem. The area under the ROC curve (AUC) was also taken into account when judging the efficacy of a classifier.

Figure 1 : Flowchart of methodology

The steps that require to be followed are:

1. Data Collection
2. Data Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Analyzing
5. Result

A. Data Collection

Drebin-215 and Malgenome-215 are two datasets of malware samples taken from the public domain. Both datasets have 215 features divided across four feature sets: (i)API calls- method names extracted from the apk's.dex file, (ii)Manifest permissions- permissions declared in the apk's AndroidManifest.xml file, (iii)Intents- used for communication with other apps/services declared in the apk's AndroidManifest.xml file, and (iv)Command signatures- linux commands found in the apk's. dex files.

B. Data Pre-processing

As previously stated, the first step was obtaining the datasets from the internet: Drebin215 and Malgenome-215. On both datasets, values were first verified. There were a few instances of missing values in the dataset. These occurrences have been removed. We looked for shared characteristics between the two datasets before integrating them. We discovered that the datasets shared 208 features, thus the remaining features were removed.

C. Applying Machine Learning Algorithm

Three classifiers were used in this study: Decision Tree, K-Nearest Neighbour, and Random Forest. Hyperparameter tuning for each of the classifiers was done on the train set using stratified 10-fold cross validation. The overall average of accuracy, f1-score, and AUC generated from 10-fold cross validation were used to evaluate a hyperparameter. The F1-score was employed to solve the issue of class imbalance, while the AUC was used to assess the adequacy of a classifier. GridSearchCV was used to search through a large number of hyperparameter values in order to identify the optimal one. Finally, the test set was used to assess the classifiers using the selected hyperparameters.

V. BUILD MODEL

The model building is the main step in the in any Machine Learning Algorithm. The steps involved in model building are as follows:

1. Import the needed packages.

```

import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
  
```

2. Read the data from the dataset using pandas.

```

df = pd.read_csv('Main_Dataset.csv')
X = df.drop('class', axis = 1)
y = df['class']
  
```

- On the train set, stratified 10-fold cross validation was used..

```
from sklearn.model_selection import StratifiedKFold, cross_val_score
cv = StratifiedKFold(n_splits=10, random_state=42, shuffle=True)
num_trees = [x for x in range(1,50)]
```

- GridSearchCV is used to search through a set of hyperparameter values:

a) Random Forest

```
from sklearn.model_selection import GridSearchCV
param_grid = {'n_estimators': np.arange(1, 50), 'max_features': ['log2', 'sqrt', 0.5]}
rf = RandomForestClassifier(random_state=42)
randomForest_gscv = GridSearchCV(rf, param_grid, cv=cv,
                                scoring=['accuracy', 'f1', 'roc_auc'],
                                refit='accuracy', n_jobs=-1)
randomForest_gscv.fit(X,y)
randomForest_gscv.best_params_
y_predict = randomForest_gscv.predict(X)
```

b) K- Nearest Neighbour

```
knn_model_gscv = KNeighborsClassifier(metric='minkowski', p=2)
param_grid = {'n_neighbors': np.arange(1, 30)}
knn_gscv = GridSearchCV(knn_model_gscv, param_grid,
                        scoring=['accuracy', 'f1', 'roc_auc'],
                        refit='accuracy', cv=cv)
knn_gscv.fit(X, y)
knn_gscv.best_params_
knn_gscv.best_score_
y_predict = knn_gscv.predict(X)
```

c) Decision Tree

```
param_grid = {'max_depth': np.arange(1, 30), 'criterion': ['gini', 'entropy']}
decisionTree_gscv = GridSearchCV(decisionTree_model_gscv, param_grid,
                                  scoring=['accuracy', 'f1', 'roc_auc'],
                                  refit='accuracy', cv=cv)
decisionTree_gscv.fit(X, y)
decisionTree_gscv.best_params_
decisionTree_gscv.best_score_
y_predict = decisionTree_gscv.predict(X)
```

- Predict the accuracy, F1-score, precision and recall on the train set.

```
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, precision_score, recall_score, f1_score
print("-----RANDOM FOREST-----")
print('Evaluation on experimenting/test dataset')
rfac_train = accuracy_score(y, y_predict)
print('Accuracy:', round(accuracy_score(y, y_predict), 3))
print('Precision:', round(precision_score(y, y_predict), 3))
print('Recall:', round(recall_score(y, y_predict), 3))
print('F1-score:', round(f1_score(y, y_predict), 3))
```

- Read the test dataset using pandas

```
holdout_df = pd.read_csv('Holdout_Dataset.csv')
holdout_df.shape

X_holdout = holdout_df.drop('class', axis = 1)
y_holdout = holdout_df['class']
```

- Predict the accuracy, F1-score, precision and recall on the test set.

```
y_holdout_predict = randomForest_gscv.predict(X_holdout)
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, precision_score, recall_score, f1_score
print('Evaluation on holdout dataset')
rfac_test = accuracy_score(y_holdout, y_holdout_predict)
print('Accuracy:', round(accuracy_score(y_holdout, y_holdout_predict), 3))
print('Precision:', round(precision_score(y_holdout, y_holdout_predict), 3))
print('Recall:', round(recall_score(y_holdout, y_holdout_predict), 3))
print('F1-score:', round(f1_score(y_holdout, y_holdout_predict), 3))
```

- Finally draw the ROC curve.

```
y_holdout_probs = randomForest_gscv.predict_proba(X_holdout)
y_holdout_probs = y_holdout_probs[:,1]
fpr, tpr, threshold = roc_curve(y_holdout, y_holdout_probs)
roc_auc = roc_auc_score(y_holdout, y_holdout_probs)

plt.title('Random Forest test-set ROC-Curve')
plt.plot(fpr, tpr, 'b', label = 'AUC = %0.3f' % roc_auc)
plt.legend(loc = 'lower right')
plt.plot([0, 1], [0, 1], 'r--')
plt.ylabel('True Positive Rate', fontsize=18)
plt.xlabel('False Positive Rate', fontsize=18)
plt.show()
```

VI. RESULT

The results shows the accuracies, F1-scores, precision and recall obtained by applying the three Machine Learning algorithms (Random Forest, K-NN, and Decision Tree). The result also plots the ROC curve for the various used algorithms.

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Random Forest	0.963	0.964	0.931	0.947
KNN	0.961	0.963	0.929	0.946
Decision Tree	0.961	0.963	0.929	0.946

Table 1: Accuracy score, precision , recall and F1-scores of various algorithms.

Figure 2: Random Forest ROC-curve

Figure 3: KNN ROC-curve

Figure 4: Decision Tree ROC-curve

Figure 5: Accuracy

Figure 6 : Bar graph showing the accuracy of different possible ML approaches

VII. CONCLUSION

Android's market share is rapidly increasing. In addition to smartphones, the platform has been combined with android Tv, wearables, smart automobiles, as well as other smart devices. With increased popularity comes more security concerns, therefore one of the most important jobs is to preserve a user's privacy and security. As a result, detecting and blocking the spread of such malware is critical. In this paper, I looked at machine learning classifiers for detecting malware on Android based on static information. Drebin and Malgenome are two datasets that I have gathered. I used three different classifiers: Decision Tree, KNN, and Random Forest, and discovered that Random Forest, an ensemble machine learning algorithm, performed the best. On the test set, Random Forest reported accuracy of 0.963, precision of 0.964, recall of 0.931, f1 score of 0.947, and AUC of 0.993.

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